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EXTENDED ABSTRACT

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SVD-ROM: Scalable Reduced Order Modeling of Weather and Climate Data Using the Singular Value Decomposition

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1. Introduction and objectives

Despite their high dimensionality, datasets in fluid dynamics, weather, and climate often exhibit low-rank structure, where a small number of dominant patterns explain most of the variability. Singular Value Decomposition (SVD)-based methods provide efficient and interpretable tools for dimensionality reduction in such systems. Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) extends this framework to time-resolved data by extracting coherent spatio-temporal structures and their associated dynamics [Schmid(2022)]. This enables the construction of low-dimensional, interpretable emulators of complex dynamical systems. However, its adoption is limited by the practical challenges of working with modern geophysical data volumes. In this work, we present SVD-ROM [Salvador-Jasin(2026)], an open-source Python package for SVD-based reduced order modeling, including DMD, designed to operate efficiently on datasets such as ERA5 using parallel and out-of-core computation on standard hardware.

2. Methods and data

SVD-ROM enables the application of DMD to datasets larger than memory through two key components: randomized SVD and optimized DMD. The randomized SVD [Halko(2011)] provides an approximate matrix factorization that is both computationally efficient and robust to noise compared to deterministic approaches. When combined with a communication-efficient, parallel QR factorization for tall-and-skinny matrices (TSQR) [Benson(2013)], it enables scalable low-rank approximations of arbitrarily large, moderately wide matrices [Tepper(2016)]. Once the SVD factors have been computed, an optimized and noise-aware formulation of DMD [Askham(2018)] is applied to the reduced representation, allowing the dominant spatio-temporal modes to be extracted efficiently without revisiting the full dataset. In practice, this enables the computation of DMD on ERA5 subsets of approximately 60 GB on a 32 GB, 10-core laptop in under 20 minutes, comparable to the cost of computing a sliding-window

climatology on the same dataset. SVD-ROM employs Dask for parallel, out-of-core computation, and the Zarr and netCDF formats for compressed chunked storage and fast data access.

3. Preliminary results

DMD models were fitted to two 60 GB subsets of the 0.25° ERA5 dataset, each consisting of a 10-year time series of global atmospheric temperature at 850 hPa with 6-hourly resolution. The first subset spans January 2010 to December 2019, while the second spans July 2010 to June 2020. Figure 1 shows the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Anomaly Correlation Coefficient (ACC) for reconstructions of the final two months of training data and for 45-day forecasts from both models. The results are compared against short-term climatology (2010–2019) and long-term climatology (1990–2019). DMD forecasts match the climatology RMSE throughout the forecast horizon, indicating that the model captures variability at a level comparable to baseline statistical benchmarks. While the ACC is low, it remains positive, indicating that the forecasts retain limited but non-random skill over extended lead times. Considering the fitted model occupies under 1.5 GB on disk, the results highlight the capability of DMD to provide a highly compressed, low-dimensional operator that captures the dominant spatio-temporal dynamics while enabling efficient storage, analysis, and forecasting.

Figure 1. RMSE of atmospheric temperature at 850 hPa for a two month reconstruction and a 45-day forecast (left), and ACC of the 45-day forecast (right), for winter (top) and summer (bottom) 2020.

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